

*Extending Anthophila research through
image and trait digitization (Big-Bee) annual
cumulative report*

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Year 4: September 01, 2024 - August 31, 2025

Accomplishments:

Major Project Goals:

The goal of Big-Bee is to expand bee research through the digitization of bee traits and images. To accomplish this goal, we will create over 1.2M images of over 5K bee species and share these images via the Bee Library and through published curated datasets. These goals will be accomplished using many methods, including developing novel Notes from Nature measurement tools.

The digitization goals of Big-Bee are (Table 1):

1. 572,813 newly digitized specimens of 5,509 target taxa. The focus is on complete digitization, which includes georeferencing and images with both specimens and labels.
2. ca. 109,000 high-resolution, focus-stacked Exemplar and Diagnostic images, including focal taxa and bee parasites.
3. 10,300 3D Image Suites for 3D image reconstruction.
4. Score Morphological Traits from images, including Body Size, Hair Color, and Hairiness.
5. Score Life History Traits from literature, including Phenology, Nesting Biology, Sociality, and Biotic Associations (Floral Specialization, Parasites, and Pathogens).

Data and images will be discoverable via iDigBio, GBIF, Bee Library (Symbiota database), and as published curated datasets.

Digitizing institution	Digitized specimens	Focus-stacked images	3D image suites	Additional Images
Arizona State University (ASUHC)	10,000	0	0	
California Academy of Sciences (CAS)	142,325	5,474	500	
Florida State Collection of Arthropods (FSCA)	90,495	5,294	500	
Harvard University (MCZ)	52,324	6,492	500	
Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT)	2,000	0	0	2,000 (microCT)
Natural History Museum of Los Angeles County (LACM)	72,681	6,543	500	
San Diego Natural History Museum (SDMC)	14,224	797	3,000	

University of California-Berkeley (EMEC)	69,297	9,892	100	
University of California, Santa Barbara (UCSB)	8,697	5,092	4,000	
University of Colorado (UCMC)	62,677	10,160	100	
University of Kansas (SEMC)	9,495	28,185	100	
University of Michigan Museum of Zoology (UMMZ)	27,815	15,198	500	
University of New Hampshire Collection of Insects and Arthropods (UNHC)	6,783	12,850	500	1,000 (CLSM)
USGS Native Bee Inventory and Monitoring Lab (USGS BIML)	4,000	4,000	0	
Total:	572,813	109,977	10,300	3,000

Table 1: Digitization goals outlining the 572K specimens to be published and digitized using multiple imaging modalities; 109K high-resolution, focus-stacked exemplar and diagnostic images; 10,300 3D image suites consisting of ~64 focus-stacked images per suite; and 3,000 CT or CLSM images. Grey highlighted rows indicate non-funded partners.

Biodiversity Informatics goals are:

1. Create the Bee Library as a Symbiota portal dedicated to bees and bee traits;
 - a. expand Symbiota’s ability to link to external resources, including the ability to link to externally managed literature (via Weblink DOI), observations (e.g., iNaturalist), other image datasets (e.g., CT, CLSM, and 3D models held outside of ASU), and other related specimens;
 - b. investigate options for sharing Image View (e.g., dorsal, ventral) as a property in Audubon Core in Symbiota;
 - c. extend the Symbiota Trait Management Tools developed by the CAP TCN to manage bee traits from both literature and specimen sources;
 - d. extend the image and dataset search capabilities in Symbiota based on locality, taxon, and view; and
 - e. Add bee observation collections.
2. Publish versioned datasets of the textual trait data and “training datasets” of image data as products;
3. Establish connections between Big-Bee Global Biotic Interactions, iDigBio, and GBIF;
4. Investigate computer vision for traits and improved methods for 3D image reconstruction;

5. Integrate additional bee data from network collections, monitoring programs, and federal collections (e.g., USGS, USDA, Smithsonian) via established IPTs or spreadsheet uploads; and
6. Participate in the OpenTraits Network.

Outreach, workforce training, and broader impact goals:

1. Create a Research Advisory Board;
2. Provide digitization resources for all global bee collections, including the ability to digitize specimens through the Big-Bee Symbiota portal and support from a portal data manager to help train and facilitate the upload and data sharing;
3. Participate fully with the Bee Monitoring USDA-RCN;
4. Create a science-themed radio program about bees;
5. Contribute lesson plans to BLUE (Biodiversity Literacy for Undergraduate Education);
6. Continue efforts to recruit students from underrepresented groups;
7. Provide opportunities for all participants to advance skills in biodiversity information science, bee identification, high-resolution imaging, museum curation, and outreach.
 - a. 3D and high-resolution imaging provided by Mark Smith, owner and developer of Macroscopic Solutions, LLC;
 - b. data curation and workflows using the Symbiota portal, including georeferencing, data management, trait annotation, and Bee Library dataset creation;
 - c. annotating and defining traits in the Bee Library;
 - d. creating a citizen science bee inventory using the Bee Library to create identification tools.
 - e. online bee morphology and Bee Library workshops will be developed in years two and three of the project. The first will focus on bee male genitalia and it will include how to prepare specimens and use the Bee Library for identification by comparing images to dissected specimens. In year three, a two-day virtual workshop on bee identification and trait determination will train novel bee researchers on how best to use the Bee Library to inform their identification efforts.
 - f. two undergraduate computer science projects will be developed by a Postdoctoral Researcher at UCSB for incorporation into the recently funded NSF “HDR DSC: Collaborative Research: Central Coast Data Science Partnership: Training a New Generation of Data Scientists” initiative.

Accomplishments Under These Goals:

Big-Bee’s overarching goal is to expand bee research by digitizing bee traits and images at scale, making these products discoverable through community infrastructure (Bee Library/Symbiota, GBIF, iDigBio) and as curated datasets; across the project to date, the network has produced **531,513 images** and digitized **330,390 new specimens** (labels transcribed with specimen images), alongside a Symbiota-based Bee Library now hosting **>4 million bee occurrence records** and a Global Bee Interaction Dataset exceeding **2.5 million interaction records**. Together these datasets enable taxonomy, ecology, and monitoring

applications. The project has an exemplary publication record, generating **36 peer-reviewed journal publications (published or under review), 63 posters and talks, and 23 shared datasets** or workshop reports, far more than any prior TCN. This success demonstrates the intrinsic research value of collections and shows that participating in digitization as a form of data collection can inspire and lead directly to novel research publications.

All institutions funded by the grant were fully engaged and successfully contributed to the project in the 2024/25 reporting period (see participant list at end of document for institution details). UNR finished their funding in 2024 and is not part of this report but is included in tables for reference. UCB is the only institution in the project requesting a NCE for 2026.

Major Accomplishments: September 1, 2021 - August 31, 2025

- 531,513 images, 330,390 new specimens digitized
 - Symbiota portal (Bee Library) with >4M bee records
 - Bee interaction dataset with > 2.5M records
 - **36 peer-reviewed journal publications, 63 posters and talks, and 23 shared datasets or workshop reports.**
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Digitization: Big-Bee digitized 330,390 new specimens (labels transcribed with specimen images), achieving 58% of our original goal (Table 2). Reported georeferencing totals are likely underestimated because some institutions do not consistently distinguish between records that are transcribed versus fully georeferenced.

	2022	2023	2024	2025
Label with Specimen Images	58,014	186,696	297,239	330,390
New specimens data transcribed	12,163	53,699	69,350	303,140
New specimens georeferenced	11,296	39,272	52,693	178,448
Focus-stacked Exemplar Images	4,300	22,618	34,439	46,277
Focus-stacked Diagnostic Images	591	712	1,322	7,978
Image Suites for 3D image reconstruction		99	459	1,040
MicroCT/CLSM				1,221
Total Images	74,201	263,158	449,953	531,513

Table 2: Cumulative digitization progress of the project. Total images include ca. 140 focus-stacked images for each 3D image suite suitable for photogrammetry reconstruction. Originally, we estimated that 64 images were needed per suite, but this number was increased to improve model clarity.

Imaging outputs: Our Diagnostic Images, Exemplar images, and 3D reconstruction image suites are multi-stacked image sets captured with the Macropod Pro imaging system; each stack (i.e., one final image product) typically includes ~70 source images. We produced 54,255 Diagnostic + Exemplar Images, reaching 42% of the 109,977 target. For 3D image suites, our goal was 10,300, and we produced 1,040 (10%).

Overall, high-resolution imaging and especially 3D imaging required substantially more time than originally estimated. Nevertheless, these products have high research value (see Significant Products below) and have enabled new methods and analyses that are already supporting sustained imaging workflows at multiple institutions and contributing to peer-reviewed outputs (see Cumulative Products and Impacts). For example, KU and UCSB are continuing a project to generate 3D models representing all bee genera worldwide to study body plan evolution and to estimate thermal tolerance using surface area-based metrics. This effort is expected to exceed 10,000 3D models, but will extend beyond the grant period.

Digitization Progress Per Institution: Although the project is finalized for all institutions except UCB, digitization is continuing especially 3D imaging.

	UNHC	UMMZI	UCSB	FSCA	SEMC	SDMC	UCMC	CAS	EMEC	LACM	ASUHC	MCZ	Total
Label with Specimen Images	2,100	26,801	11,736	30,520	0	8,216	60,955	50,475	63,136	37,520	4,524	34,407	330,390
New specimen data transcribed	0	19,211	11,399	30,520	0	9,029	122,873	2,873	38,421	34,407	0	34,407	303,140
New specimens georeferenced	0	624	11,399	19,657	0	5,478	82,518	0	24,365	0	0	34,407	178,448
Focus-stacked exemplar images	3,472	3,781	3,786	1,810	12,222	510	4,090	3,261	4,351	542	4,524	3,928	46,277
Focus-stacked diagnostic images	2,520	0	5,308	0	150	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7,978
Number of images for 3D suites	0	12,999	26,600	0	11,760	29,689	12,999	0	840	17,240	0	33,520	145,647
3D specimens	108	1	190	0	84	143	104	0	6	0	0	115	1,040
microCT/CLSM	1,221	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1,221
Total images	9,313	43,581	47,430	32,330	24,132	38,415	78,044	53,736	68,327	55,302	9,048	71,855	531,513

Table 3: Digitization per Institution.

MicroCT and CLSM Imaging:

UNH led an effort to image male and female genitalia using microCT and CLSM methods. This has resulted in 1,221 micrographs (Figure 1). UNH's microCT and CLSM imaging of male and female genitalia is important because it produces high-resolution, 3D reference data for characters that are often essential for species identification, delimitation, and phylogenetic work, but are poorly captured with standard 2D imaging. MicroCT enables non-destructive volumetric anatomy, while CLSM provides fine surface/detail contrast, together improving repeatability and cross-study comparability and enabling quantitative morphometrics. The resulting 1,221 micrographs are a reusable digital resource that can be linked to specimen records, broaden access beyond physical specimen loans, and support future computer-vision and AI-assisted identification and morphology research. UCSB received a USDA NIFA equipment grant at the end of 2023 to continue researching bee internal morphology as it relates to nesting habits and health stressors.

Figure 1: CLSM images of *Colletes* (left) and microCT of *Andrena* (right) male genitalia.

Macroscopic Solutions: Mark Smith, founder and CEO of Macroscopic Solutions continued to work with Big-Bee this year although the amount of effort was less because the Big-Bee participants were more self-sufficient in imaging. This collaboration has led to improvement in the 3D imaging technology (see **What is the impact on technology transfer?**) and many online resources about how to do 3D imaging of small objects (See **How have results been disseminated to communities of interest?**, below).

Notes from Nature: To support label transcription and bee body-size measurement, UNR built a custom Notes from Nature project for Big-Bee in Year 1, Big-Bee Bonanza (<https://www.zooniverse.org/projects/md68135/notes-from-nature-big-bee-bonanza>). This project is continuing beyond the grant to transcribe labels in support of ongoing digitization at LACM, EMEC, and UCMC. To date, **4,783 volunteers** have contributed **105,613 completed specimen transcriptions and body size measurements**.

The measurement component has now ended, but its outcomes are published in *Ecology and Evolution* as “Leveraging Community Science to Measure Bee Body Size from Museum Specimens.” That study evaluates whether community scientists can reliably estimate

bee body size from specimen images by measuring intertegular distance (ITD) in Notes from Nature. Compared with trained-researcher measurements, volunteer measurements showed high completion (successful measurement of ~98% of images; ~43.6 specimens per user on average). Volunteer measurements were slightly but significantly larger than researcher measurements, but average error was small (~2.3%), indicating that this approach can efficiently generate large, usable body-size datasets when that error level is acceptable. These measurement expeditions produced a dataset of ~12,000 specimens from North America, spanning 24 genera and 165 species.

This dataset is now being analyzed for evidence of body-size change over time and will be released in full upon submission of the resulting manuscript. Preliminary results suggest that bee body size has decreased in California (Figure 2), where sampling is sufficient to evaluate multi-year trends across taxa.

Figure 2: Preliminary data from Notes from Nature measurements show a decrease in bee community body size across California.

Bee Library Symbiota Portal: The Big-Bee Symbiota portal (Bee Library - <https://library.big-bee.net>) was rapidly launched in the first quarter of the project (October 2021). The portal continues to be managed by the Symbiota Support Hub. During this year, the Bee Library and Symbiota Support Hub moved to the University of Kansas, home of the Snow Entomology Collection, one of the most important bee collections in the United States and a partner in this project. The Bee Library will continue in the near term with support from ongoing efforts of the Native Bee Monitoring program led by Hollis Woodard (UC Riverside), Victor H. Gonzalez Betancourt (Michener Assistant Professor/Curator of Bee Biodiversity and Evolution), Katja Seltmann (UCSB Cheadle Center), and the Support Hub staff and PI. The Bee Library's core strengths are (1) bringing U.S. bee occurrence records together in one place and (2)

servicing as a publication platform that streamlines delivery of bee monitoring data to GBIF. To further enable consistent, interoperable data publishing, PI Seltmann and co-authors, in collaboration with the Bee Monitoring RCN, published a Journal of Melittology article, "Improving the standardization of wild bee occurrence data: Towards a formal wild bee data standard." The paper introduces the Wild Bee Data Standard to reduce inconsistency in how wild bee occurrence records (from specimens and photo observations) are recorded and shared, and it provides practical resources, including recommended terms, templates, a glossary, and guidance for translating legacy datasets. It also highlights Symbiota portals, including the Bee Library, as essential infrastructure for managing occurrence data, hosting images, and publishing standardized datasets to aggregators such as GBIF. Currently, portal management of the Bee Library will continue with UCSB/HUB but conversations are continuing about distribution of management support and funding for the HUB to continue maintaining this important resource.

The Bee Library currently hosts **4,188,016** occurrence records (up from **3,501,173 last year**) from **72** collections. **87%** of the specimens are georeferenced, **22%** contain images, and **85%** are identified to species (retrieved November 26, 2025). All Big-Bee participants are sharing data with the Bee Library, but the largest boost in participation continues to come outside of the funded collaborators, demonstrating broad support of the Big-Bee Library portal in the bee community.

In Project Year 3, the Symbiota Support Hub configured the Bee Library to enable data publishing to GBIF from this data portal. Software updates (Symbiota 3.1) and hotfixes were regularly deployed to the portal. On November 5, 2024, two Symbiota Support Hub representatives (Katie Pearson, Lindsay Walker) visited PI Seltmann at UCSB to offer in-person support for the Bee Library. Guidance was offered to both funded and unfunded project collaborators, such as the Texas Native Bee RCN. Six new data providers were added to the Bee Library in Year 3: 1) University of North Texas' Bee Literature dataset (721 records); 2) the University of Texas at Austin Jha Lab Insect Collection (14,022 records); 3) Malheur National Forest Native Bee Collection (5,743 records); 4) Steens Mountain Native Bee Collection (15,954 records); 5) Sam Houston State University's Pascarella Bee Biodiversity Collections (data transfer pending); and 6) University of California San Diego Holway Lab (data transfer pending).

Global Biotic Interactions: Big-Bee is sharing in a single, aligned dataset with ca. **2.5 million** bee interactions as part of the Global Bee Interaction Dataset. This dataset has been downloaded over 2,000 times and is currently being used in several research and conservation-based products. This Big-Bee product will continue after the funding for this grant has ended.

Seltmann, K. C., Poelen, J. H., & Global Biotic Interaction Community. (2025). Global Bee Interaction Data (v6.0) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17715382>

A cleaned-up version of this dataset was submitted in 2025 to Scientific Data and is currently under review. "Tackling the Eltonian shortfall for bees using the Global Biotic Interactions dataset" compiles, cleans, and taxonomically harmonizes a global subset of GloBI focused on bee-plant interactions. The authors standardize bee and plant names against current checklists

and enrich records with metadata on geography, endemism, and human uses of host plants, producing a curated dataset of 482,617 unique interaction records linking 4,560 bee species to 8,651 plant taxa (7,398 at species level). Key results show that, despite its scale, the dataset is strongly biased taxonomically and geographically: it captures only ~21% of described bee species globally and about ~2.5% of flowering plant taxa, and is heavily skewed toward North America and Western Europe (e.g., North America contains ~95% of the coordinated interaction records). The plant side is also biased toward species used by people with ~54% of the plant species are documented as used by humans.

Seltmann and Poelen continue to maintain a data monitoring page at <https://globalbioticinteractions.org/bigbee> to review and track the availability of Big-Bee-associated natural history collections. These reviews are linked through shared IPT or Darwin Core archives and involve assessing taxon names, the number of biotic interactions, and data structure.

What opportunities for training and professional development has the project provided?

A weekly meeting via Zoom continued to be an important part of creating Big-Bee workflows, supporting project organization, and onboarding new participants. The Zoom meetings were well attended by participants, Symbiota Support Hub staff, project consultants, Macroscopic Solutions staff, and other project collaborators. The meetings also provided a venue for imaging training by Mark Smith (Macroscopic Solutions). They provided much-needed open office time for questions.

Big-Bee used Slack to enhance communication. We had 123 members on Slack, including project PIs, collaborators, Symbiota Support Hub staff, undergraduates, and technicians. Slack was used for day-to-day project management and for training and communication about imaging, Notes from Nature, and other project goals.

Additional training activities were facilitated by the Symbiota Support Hub as part of the aforementioned Portal Advancement Campaign on the topics of data ingestion, data publishing, and research use of the Bee Library data portal.

Macroscopic Solutions actively engaged in support channels through email, the [macroscopicolutions.com](https://www.macroscopicolutions.com) support forum, YouTube, and Slack. They hosted a new podcast series (<https://www.youtube.com/@macropod/podcasts>) in which scientists with niche imaging questions asked Macroscopic Solutions for insight or instructions. The podcast opened these questions to a larger community and shared protocols in an open-source manner. Similarly, their YouTube channel (<https://www.youtube.com/@macropod/videos>) and forum (<https://macroscopicolutions.com/forum/official-forum>) served as hubs for individuals seeking how-to guides and instructions for focus stacking and 3D photogrammetry techniques.

How have results been disseminated to communities of interest?

- A total of **5** student oral presentations, **11** student posters, **15** student research projects, and **19** published (or in review) scholarly articles this year.
- Big-Bee was mentioned in **12** academic presentations this year.

- Big-Bee was presented or discussed in **81 events** (i.e., open houses, collection tours) across the network, with **15,260 attendees**.
- Rather than developing independent help resources, Big-Bee continued to help develop the Symbiota Support Hub (<https://symbiota.org/help-resources>) and Macroscopic Solutions help resources for the entire community.
- Big-Bee used a Zenodo Community (<https://zenodo.org/communities/bigbee/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>) to highlight and archive our resources and datasets.
- Macroscopic Solutions created open-source PDFs and tutorial videos describing photogrammetric workflows. These videos are accessible on Macroscopic Solutions YouTube channel and website. Since creating this content, Macroscopic Solutions has seen a sharp increase in academic-based subscriptions. (Examples: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCXhbJ-JirA3-J7FihjXtUyg> and <https://macroscopicsolutions.com/video-tutorial-big-bee-tcn/>)
- Big-Bee is represented via our websites, GitHub project, and data portals (see Products). The Bee Library Symbiota portal was visited by ca. **6,600** users between September 01, 2024 - November 26, 2025. The majority of the users found the Bee Library by direct or organic search.

What do you plan to do during the next reporting period to accomplish the goals?

- Only UC Berkeley requested a no-cost-extension for this project.

Cumulative Products

To date, the project has produced **36** peer-reviewed journal publications, **63** posters and talks, and **23** shared datasets or workshop reports.

Published Journal Articles:

1. Noori, S., Hughes, A., Vasconcelos, T., Ascher, J. S., Miller, J. T., Gaugel, S. M., Ostwald, M. M., Dorey, J., Gonzalez, V. H., Martins, A., Orr, M. C., & Seltmann, K. C. (in review). Tackling the Eltonian shortfall for bees using the Global Biotic Interactions dataset (preprint, v1). Scientific Data. Authorea. <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.175822523.37965920/v1>
2. Lee M., DiRenzo G., Diao C., Seltmann K.C. (In review). Leveraging local and regional sources of data and a multi-species occupancy model to explore bee-plant interactions. Ecological Applications.
3. Zabinski, W. J., & Cook, J.L. (In review). A new species of *Stylops* Pierce (Strepsiptera: Stylopidae) from China, the second to parasitize a member of the subgenus *Oreomelissa* of *Andrena* (Hymenoptera: Andrenidae). Journal of the Kansas Entomological Society

4. Baena-Díaz, F., Morales-Gómez, M., Ratoní, B., Gonzalez, V.H., & W. Dáttilo. (In review). General patterns and predictors of thermal tolerance in bees: A synthesis across taxa and environments. *Journal of Thermal Biology*.
5. Bossert, S., Zabinski, W.J., & J.L. Neff. (In review). A new species of *Andrena* (*LaBergeia*) from Texas with unusual phenology and floral hosts. *Journal of Melittology*
6. Guevara, D., Gonzalez, V.H., & Ospina, R. (In review). New species and records of stingless bees (Hymenoptera: Apidae: Meliponini) for Colombia. *Journal of Melittology*
7. Herrera, A., Penichet, C., Gonzalez, V.H., & J. Soberón. (In review). Neotropical dry forests host diverse bee communities despite conservation and taxonomical challenges. *Journal of Insect Conservation*.
8. Zabinski, W. J. (In review). An extraordinary northward range extension of *Andrena* (*Cnemidandrena*) *pachucensis* Donovan, 1977 (Hymenoptera, Andrenidae) to New Mexico, USA. *Check List*.
9. Zabinski, W. J. (In review). Flower associations and phenology of North American bees in the genus *Andrena* (Hymenoptera: Andrenidae) subgenus *Plastandrena*. *Journal of Pollination Ecology*.
10. Du Clos, B., Seltmann, K. C., Turley, N. E., Maffei, C., Tucker, E. M., Lane, I. G., Levenson, H. K., & Woodard, S. H. (2025) Improving the standardization of wild bee occurrence data: Towards a formal wild bee data standard. *Journal of Melittology* 123(3): 1–61. <https://doi.org/10.17161/jom.vi123.23163>
11. Ostwald, M., Hirokawa, R., Smith, C., Rivas Trasvina, S., & Seltmann, K. C. (2025) Estimating body size in the large carpenter bees (*Xylocopa*). *Journal of Melittology* 125: 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.17161/jom.vi125.23025>
12. Ostwald, M. M., Chen, K., Alexander, N., Ding, L., Gonzalez, V. H., & Seltmann, K. C. (2025) Climate explains global functional trait variation in bees. *Functional Ecology* 39(7): 1748–1760. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2435.70051>
13. Ostwald, M. M., Smith, C., Allen, J., Buetow, A., Manner, A. R., Guralnick, R., Goldsmith, C., & Seltmann, K. C. (2025) Leveraging community science to measure bee body size from museum specimens. *Ecology and Evolution* 15(6): e71665. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ece3.71665>
14. Smith, C., Bachelder, N., Russell, A. L., et al. (2025) Pollen specialist bee species are accurately predicted from visitation, occurrence and phylogenetic data. *Oecologia* 207: 13. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00442-024-05653-5>
15. Martins, A. C., Heinrich, L., Hughes, A. C., Seltmann, K. C., Orr, M. C., & Vasconcelos, T. (2025) Plant communities in the Americas are highly bee dependent regardless of biome or local bee diversity. *Global Ecology and Biogeography* 34(8): e70101. <https://doi.org/10.1111/geb.70101>
16. Awad, J., Brar, G., Cadwalader, E., et al. (2025) Defining the decline: a glossary relevant to insect decline. *Journal of Insect Science* 25(3): 4. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jisesa/ieaf048>
17. Wyatt J. Zabinski and Natalie D. Herbison. (2025) *Stylops* Kirby, 1802 (Strepsiptera: Stylopidae) parasitizing bees in the *Andrena* Fabricius, 1775 subgenus *Callandrena* Cockerell, 1898 (Hymenoptera: Andrenidae), with description of a new species. *The Pan-Pacific Entomologist* 101(2), 184-194. <https://doi.org/10.3956/2025-101.2.184>

18. Jerry L. Cook and Wyatt J. Zabinski. (2025). A New Species of *Triozocera* Pierce (Strepsiptera: Corioxenidae) from Arizona, USA, with a Key to Species in North America, *Journal of the Kansas Entomological Society* 98(1), 1-9.
<https://doi.org/10.2317/0022-8567-98.1.1>
19. Gonzalez, V.H., Wiggins, K.L., Bonnell, K., & J. Girón. (2025). A framework for the assessment of outreach drawers in insect collections. *Natural History Collections and Museomics* 2:1–12. <https://doi.org/10.3897/nhcm.2.153644>
20. Guevara, D., Gonzalez, V.H., Ospina, R. & D.W. Roubik. (2025). A new species of *Duckeanthidium* Moure & Hurd (Megachilidae: Anthidiini) from Colombia, with notes on *D. thielei* Michener in Panama. *Journal of Melittology* 130:1–7.
<https://doi.org/10.17161/jom.vi130.23313>
21. G.W. Frankie, S.L. Witt, J.C. Pawelek, B. Faber, R.E. Coville, M.A. Rizzardi, M.H. Chase, J. O’Sullivan, K.C. Seltmann. (2024) Hedgerow Gardens Provide Floral Resources for Diverse Insect Visitors to Avocado Flowers in Southern California. *Journal of the Kansas Entomological Society* 96(3): 39–67.
22. Ostwald, M. M., da Silva, C. R. B., & Seltmann, K. C. (2024) How does climate change impact social bees and bee sociality? *Journal of Animal Ecology* 93(11): 1610–1621.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2656.14160>
23. Ostwald, M. M., Venegas, V. A., & Seltmann, K. C. (2024) Social conditions facilitate water conservation in a solitary bee. *Journal of Insect Science* 24(1): 1.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/jisesa/ieae001>
24. Payne, H. E., Mazer, S., & Seltmann, K. C. (2024) Native Bee Habitat Restoration: Key Ecological Considerations from Recent North American Literature. *Frontiers in Ecology and Evolution* 12: 1358621. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fevo.2024.1358621>
25. Engel, M. S. (2024) On the classification of sphecodine bees (Hymenoptera: Halictidae). *Entomologist’s Monthly Magazine* 160(1): 1–52.
26. Cook, Jerry & Zabinski, Wyatt. (2024). *Stylops* (Strepsiptera: Stylopidae) Parasitizing Bees in the Subgenus *Micrandrena* (Hymenoptera: Andrenidae: *Andrena*) in the United States, with the Description of a New Species. *Journal of the Kansas Entomological Society*. 96. [10.2317/0022-8567-96.1.6](https://doi.org/10.2317/0022-8567-96.1.6).
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28. Ostwald, M. M., Thrift, C. N., & Seltmann, K. C. (2023) Phenotypic divergence in an island bee population: Applying geometric morphometrics to discriminate population-level variation in wing venation. *Ecology and Evolution* 13: e10085.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/ece3.10085>
29. Baskauf, S. J., Girón Duque, J. C., Nielsen, M., Cobb, N. S., Singer, R., Seltmann, K. C., Kachian, Z., Pérez, M., Agosti, D., & Klompen, A. M. L. (2023) Implementation Experience Report for Controlled Vocabularies Used with the Audubon Core Terms subjectPart and subjectOrientation. *Biodiversity Information Science and Standards* 7: e94188. <https://doi.org/10.3897/biss.7.94188>
30. Engel, M. S. (2023) A new species of *Callomegachile* from Larat, Indonesia (Hymenoptera: Megachilidae). *Entomologist’s Monthly Magazine* 159(1): 13–18.

31. Engel, M. S. (2023) An illustrated key to Anthophoroides Cockerell & Cockerell, with the description of three new species (Hymenoptera: Apidae). *Entomologist's Monthly Magazine* 159: 147–167.
32. Engel, M. S. (2023) A new species of *Dioxys* Lepelletier & Audinet-Serville from southern Spain, with notes on the classification of *Dioxyini* (Hymenoptera: Megachilidae). *Entomologist's Monthly Magazine* 159: 175–182.
33. Engel, M. S. (2023) Two new species of *Clystospenella* Kieffer from Belize and Peru (Hymenoptera: Scolebythidae). *Entomologist's Monthly Magazine* 159: 197–204.
34. Engel, M. S. (2022) New species of the stingless bee genus *Plebeia* (Hymenoptera: Apidae). *Journal of Melittology* 114: 1–28.

Juried Conference Paper:

35. Seltmann KC, Allen J, Brown BV, Carper A, Engel MS, Franz N, Gilbert E, Grinter C, Gonzalez VH, Horsley P, Lee S, Maier C, Miko I, Morris P, Oboyski P, Pierce NE, Poelen J, Scott VL, Smith M, Talamas EJ, Tsutsui ND, Tucker E (2021) Announcing Big-Bee: An initiative to promote understanding of bees through image and trait digitization. *Biodiversity Information Science and Standards* 5: e74037.
<https://doi.org/10.3897/biss.5.74037>
36. Salim JA, Seltmann KC, Poelen JH, Saraiva AM (2022) Indexing Biotic Interactions in GBIF data. *Biodiversity Information Science and Standards* 6: e93565.
<https://doi.org/10.3897/biss.6.93565>

Talks/Posters:

1. Du Clos, B., Seltmann, K., Turley, N., Maffei, C., Tucker, E., Lane, I. G., Levenson, H., & Woodard, H. (2025). The wild bee data standard. Entomological Society of America (ESA) Annual Meeting, Portland, OR, United States.
2. De La Cruz, J. A., Thrift, C., Ostwald, M., & Seltmann, K. (2025). Wing venation reflects phylogenetic divergence and allometric scaling in bees. Entomological Society of America (ESA) Annual Meeting, Portland, OR, United States.
3. Thrift, C., Wood, T., & Seltmann, K. (2025). Narrow niches, narrow ranges: Linking floral specialization to geographic vulnerability in bees. Entomological Society of America (ESA) Annual Meeting, Portland, OR, United States.
4. Seltmann, K., & González, V. H. (2025). Entomological collections: Windows to the past, tools for the future. Entomological Society of America (ESA) Annual Meeting, Portland, OR, United States.
5. Park, I., & Seltmann, K. (2025). Systematic shifts in floral resource availability to generalist & specialist bees within an island ecosystem. Entomological Society of America (ESA) Annual Meeting, Portland, OR, United States.
6. Mikó I, Hoag A, Raymond M, Denardo C, and Langa M. (2025). Big Bee at the University of New Hampshire. Entomological Society of America (ESA) Annual Meeting, Portland, OR, United States.
7. Manning, I., Gonzalez, V.H., Youngblood, A., Thrift, C., & K. Seltman. Using 3D modeling to evaluate body size metrics in bee ecophysiological studies (Poster presentation). Annual Meeting of the Entomological Society of America, Portland, OR. (November 12,

- 2025) - A Spanish version of this poster will be presented in the Mesoamerican Bee Meeting, San Jose, Costa Rica (December 3, 2025).
8. Catlett, A., Gonzalez, V.H., & T. Griswold. Convergent evolution of specialized bee traits for pollen collection from nototribic flowers (Poster presentation). Annual Meeting of the Entomological Society of America, Portland, OR. (November 12, 2025)
 9. Branstetter, M., & González, V. H. (Organizers). (2025). Enhancing Bee Taxonomy via Community Building, Research Prioritization, and Innovation (panel session). Entomological Society of America (ESA) Annual Meeting, Portland, OR, United States.
 10. Seltmann, K. (2025, October 5). Entomological collections: Windows to the past, tools for the future (invited seminar). Biology Seminar Series, Georgia Southern University.
 11. Park, I. W., & Seltmann, K. (2025). Museum specimens detect systematic shifts in floral resource availability to generalist & specialist bees. Georgia Entomological Society Annual Meeting, Young Harris, GA, United States.
 12. Seltmann, K. (2025, March 6). Bee biodiversity and natural history collections (invited seminar). Department of Biology, University of Kentucky.
 13. Seltmann, K. (2025, January 13). Insect biodiversity and natural history collections: Research for conservation, innovation & societal benefits (invited seminar). EEOB, The Ohio State University.
 14. Tang, R. (2025). To Bee or Not to Bee Hairy: A Quantitative Analysis of Pilosity Across *Melissodes tepidus* Subspecies. UC Santa Barbara: Cheadle Center for Biodiversity and Ecological Restoration. Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/0x31p2g2>
 15. Bishop, B., Yan, D., Dibley, K., Sharma, K., Linden, C., Reagan, S., et al. (2025). Exploring optimizations in Anthophila taxonomic research using retrieval-augmented generation. UC Santa Barbara: Cheadle Center for Biodiversity and Ecological Restoration. Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/7975q8tn>
 16. Vargas, E. R., Ostwald, M. M., & Seltmann, K. C. (2025). Analyzing bee body size as a potential factor of the island rule. UC Santa Barbara: Cheadle Center for Biodiversity and Ecological Restoration. Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/9fp8p14t>
 17. Vo, K. A., Tran, M., Huang, J., Thrift, C., Ostwald, M., & Seltmann, K. (2025). Body size-mediated wing wear: Analyzing wing damage in native bee species using image segmentation model. UC Santa Barbara: Cheadle Center for Biodiversity and Ecological Restoration. Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/0ww2j0zm>
 18. Rosillo, E., Seltmann, K., & Evelyn, C. (2025). Machine learning to aid pollinator monitoring of endangered plants. UC Santa Barbara: Cheadle Center for Biodiversity and Ecological Restoration. Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/17n6f098>
 19. Tran, M., & Vo, K. (2025). Flying on broken wings: Wing wear analysis between mid-size Santa Barbara specialist and generalist bee species using a computer vision model. UC Santa Barbara: Cheadle Center for Biodiversity and Ecological Restoration. Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/3gc32484>
 20. Love, A. S., & Seltmann, K. C. (2025). Undergraduates in natural history collections: Educational opportunities and needs. UC Santa Barbara: Cheadle Center for Biodiversity and Ecological Restoration. Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/2kv8k9qj>

21. Reagan, S. C., Bishop, B., Linden, C., Sharma, K., Yan, D., & Dibley, K. (2025). Exploring optimizations in Anthophila taxonomic research using retrieval-augmented generation. UC Santa Barbara: Cheadle Center for Biodiversity and Ecological Restoration. Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/8xc790xx>
22. Lay, L. F. (2025). Investigating the climatic factors that influence the activity of the long horned bee *Melissodes tepida timberlakei*. UC Santa Barbara: Cheadle Center for Biodiversity and Ecological Restoration. Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/4s5364rb>
23. De La Cruz, J. A., Thrift, C. N., Ostwald, M. M., & Seltmann, K. C. (2025). Wing venation reflects phylogenetic divergence and allometric scaling in bees. UC Santa Barbara: Cheadle Center for Biodiversity and Ecological Restoration. Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/9w81x8mn>
24. Thrift, C. N., Braman, C. A., & Seltmann, K. (2024). Bee community assemblages within a California coastal sage scrub restoration context. Entomological Society of America (ESA) Annual Meeting, Phoenix, AZ, United States.
25. Seltmann, K., Ostwald, M., González, V. H., Chen, K., Ding, L., Alexander, N., & Goldsmith, C. (2024). Computer vision reveals the climatic and phylogenetic factors influencing hairiness patterns in bees. Entomological Society of America (ESA) Annual Meeting, Phoenix, AZ, United States.
26. Ostwald, M., De La Cruz, J., Thrift, C. N., & Seltmann, K. (2024). Automating bee wing analysis: Computer vision for biodiversity monitoring and evolutionary ecology research. Entomological Society of America (ESA) Annual Meeting, Phoenix, AZ, United States.
27. Oboyski, P. (2024). Engaging the community to capture specimen data: Notes from nature. Entomological Society of America (ESA) Annual Meeting, Phoenix, AZ, United States.
28. Hori, T. (2024). Coming into Focus: Standardizing the 3D image process at the San Diego Natural History Museum. Entomological Collections Network (ECN) Annual Meeting, Phoenix, AZ, United States.
29. De La Cruz, J. A., Seltmann, K. C., & Ostwald, M. M. (2024). Applying geometric morphometrics to assess phenotypic variation in bees. UC Santa Barbara: Cheadle Center for Biodiversity and Ecological Restoration. Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/9vv4k5w4>
30. Cervantes Rivera, L., Radwich, R., Ostwald, M. M., & Seltmann, K. C. (2024). Identifying the impact of body measurements on dry weight across and within bee species. UC Santa Barbara: Cheadle Center for Biodiversity and Ecological Restoration. Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/1dp4h100>
31. Radwich, R. M., Cervantes Rivera, L., Ostwald, M. M., & Seltmann, K. C. (2024). Variation in bee body size due to anthropogenic land use. UC Santa Barbara: Cheadle Center for Biodiversity and Ecological Restoration. Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/841173cj>
32. Rink, J., Kavuluru, R., Golich, D., Moon, P., Rajagopal, N., Huang, J., et al. (2024). Bee species identification: Improving population monitoring techniques. UC Santa Barbara: Cheadle Center for Biodiversity and Ecological Restoration. Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/7z6734gt>

33. Bonnet, N. H., Ostwald, M. M., & Seltmann, K. C. (2024). Physiological traits as predictors of climate resistance and sociality in female carpenter bees. UC Santa Barbara: Cheadle Center for Biodiversity and Ecological Restoration. Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/31x6m4nc>
34. You, T., Ostwald, M., & Seltmann, K. (2024). Striped ambiguity: A quantitative approach towards understanding camouflage using computer vision. UC Santa Barbara: Cheadle Center for Biodiversity and Ecological Restoration. Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/8xd7s974>
35. Seltmann, K. C. (2023, September 19–20). Big-Bee Thematic Collection Network: Key achievements and insights over the past two years (virtual presentation). Biodiversity Digitization Conference (BioDigiCon).
36. Seltmann, K. C. (2023, July 19). New and current TCNs: Parasite Tracker and Big-Bee. Entomological Collection Managers Workshop.
37. Seltmann, K. C. (2023, June 5–7). The pilosity problem: Using computer vision methods to define a complex phenotype in bees. Digital Data.
38. Ostwald, M. (2023, June 5–7). Toward a global bee functional trait database. Digital Data.
39. Miller, J. T. (2023, June 5–7). Exploring shared life-history strategies as a driver for biodiversity in desert bees & plants. Digital Data.
40. Smith, C., & Seltmann, K. C. (2023, June 1). You're it: Tagging specimen images in Symbiota to facilitate their use in research. Society for the Preservation of Natural History Collections Annual Meeting, San Francisco, CA, United States.
41. Palmrose-Krieger, C., Lee, S., & Franz, N. M. (2023, April). Big-Bee: Trait digitization to advance buzz ecology and taxonomy research (poster). 30th Annual School of Life Sciences Undergraduate Research Symposium, Arizona State University, Tempe, AZ, United States.
42. Seltmann, K. C., & Paul, D. (2023, March). Lets Talk About Data. Native Bee Monitoring RCN Data Management Workshop, Zoom.
43. Seltmann, K. C. (2023, March). Big-Bee: Sharing bee interactions & traits (talk). Native Bee Monitoring RCN Data Management Workshop, Zoom.
44. Poelen, J. (2023, March). Bee species interactions (talk). Native Bee Monitoring RCN Data Management Workshop, Zoom.
45. Poelen, J. (2023, February 28; March 28). How Big is That Bee (virtual presentations). NanoSessions #1 and #2, KnowledgePixel. Retrieved from <https://github.com/Big-Bee-Network/UCSB-IZC00012194/blob/main/nanosessions-presentation-2023-02-28.md> and <https://github.com/Big-Bee-Network/UCSB-IZC00012194/blob/main/nanosessions-presentation-2023-03-28.md>
46. Rivas Trasvina, S., Smith, C., Ostwald, M. M., & Seltmann, K. C. (2023). Exploring pilosity in the California native bee *Melissodes tepidus timberlakei* as an indicator of age and implications for pollinator response to climate change. UC Santa Barbara: Cheadle Center for Biodiversity and Ecological Restoration. Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/5zp1f28j>

47. Sanchez, E., Ostwald, M. M., Smith, C., & Seltmann, K. C. (2023). Utilizing surface area to volume ratios and thermal tolerance of various bee species to predict their performance under rising global temperatures. UC Santa Barbara: Cheadle Center for Biodiversity and Ecological Restoration. Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/6ds6j4h5>
48. Seltmann, K. C., Miller, J. T., & Poelen, J. H. (2022). Global bee interaction database. Entomological Society of America (ESA), Vancouver, BC, Canada.
49. Seltmann, K. C., Allen, J., Brown, B. V., Carper, A., Eldredge, T., Engel, M. S., Franz, N., Gilbert, E., Grinter, C., Gonzalez, V. H., Horsley, P., Kung, G. A., Lee, S., Maier, C., Miko, I., Morris, P., Oboyski, P., Ostwald, M. M., Pierce, N. E., Poelen, J., Scott, V. L., Smith, C., Smith, M., Talamas, E. J., Tsutsui, N. D., & Tucker, E. (2022). Announcing Big-Bee: An initiative to promote understanding of bees through image and trait digitization (poster). Entomological Society of America (ESA), Vancouver, BC, Canada.
50. Seltmann, K. C. (2022). Extended Thoughts about the Extended Specimen. Biodiversity Digitization Conference (BioDigiCon) (virtual presentation). Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/0g99h7kf> (mp4) on 28 Sept 2022
51. Seltmann, K. C. (2022). Extending Anthophila research through image and trait digitization: Big-Bee. Biodiversity Digitization Conference (BioDigiCon) (virtual presentation). Retrieved from https://www.idigbio.org/wiki/index.php/BioDigiCon_2022 on 27 Sept 2022
52. Allen, J. (2022, October 14). Notes from Nature: Goals, accomplishments and future directions. WeDigBio (virtual presentation).
53. Seltmann, K. C. (2022). Entomological collections management workshop: Big-Bee and Terrestrial Parasite Tracker. BioDigiCon. Retrieved from https://www.idigbio.org/wiki/index.php/BioDigiCon_2022 on 22 June 2022
54. Ostwald, M. M., Seltmann, K. C., Allen, J., Brown, B. V., Carper, A., Eldredge, T., Engel, M. S., Franz, N., Gilbert, E., Grinter, C., Gonzalez, V. H., Horsley, P., Kung, G. A., Lee, S., Maier, C., Miko, I., Morris, P., Oboyski, P., Pierce, N. E., Poelen, J., Scott, V. L., Smith, C., Smith, M., Talamas, E. J., Tsutsui, N. D., & Tucker, E. (2022). Announcing Big-Bee: An initiative to promote understanding of bees through image and trait digitization. BeeCon, York University, Toronto, Canada (virtual).
55. Seltmann, K. C., Allen, J., Brown, B. V., Carper, A., Eldredge, T., Engel, M. S., Franz, N., Gilbert, E., Grinter, C., Gonzalez, V. H., Horsley, P., Kung, G. A., Lee, S., Maier, C., Miko, I., Morris, P., Oboyski, P., Ostwald, M. M., Pierce, N. E., Poelen, J., Scott, V. L., Smith, C., Smith, M., Talamas, E. J., Tsutsui, N. D., & Tucker, E. (2022). Announcing Big-Bee: An initiative to promote understanding of bees through image and trait digitization. International Union for the Study of Social Insects (IUSSI), San Diego, CA, United States.
56. Wong-Lau, J., Klauke, H., Kaur, H., Alexander, N., Bang, J., & Seltmann, K. C. (2022). Big-Bee: Hair recognition and quantification. UC Santa Barbara: Cheadle Center for Biodiversity and Ecological Restoration. Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/0fb1n3pw>

57. Miller, J. T., & Seltmann, K. C. (2022). Environmental trends in the distribution of California bee species. UC Santa Barbara: Cheadle Center for Biodiversity and Ecological Restoration. Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/36w6x8pp>
58. Eisner de Eisenhof, L., & Seltmann, K. (2022). Body size and taxonomic influence on bee wing vein density. UC Santa Barbara: Cheadle Center for Biodiversity and Ecological Restoration. Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/0z73n6vt>
59. Xu, C., & Seltmann, K. C. (2022). Variation of ocelli size between male and female bees in species of different sociality. UC Santa Barbara: Cheadle Center for Biodiversity and Ecological Restoration. Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/0v065150>
60. González, V. H., Seltmann, K. C., Brown, B., Allen, J., Carper, A., Engel, M., et al. (2021, November 20–21). Big-Bee: Una iniciativa para promover el conocimiento de las abejas a través de la digitalización de imágenes y datos de rasgos (Poster ID 112; poster in Spanish). XII Congreso Mesoamericano de Abejas Nativas, Centro de Investigaciones Apícolas Tropicales (CINAT), Universidad Nacional, Costa Rica. Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/0856h3d2>
61. Seltmann, K., Allen, J., Brown, B. V., Carper, A., Engel, M. S., Franz, N., et al. (2021). Announcing Big-Bee: An initiative to promote understanding of bees through image and trait digitization. *Biodiversity Information Science and Standards*, 5(e74037). Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/0937b5gp>
62. Seltmann, K. C. (2021). New TCN: Big-Bee. Virtual ADBC Summit (presentation for iDigBio and the ADBC program). Retrieved from https://www.idigbio.org/wiki/index.php/ADBC_Summit_2021 on 21 Sept 2021
63. Thrift, C. N., & Seltmann, K. C. (2021). Identifying island-mainland bee populations with wings. UC Santa Barbara: Cheadle Center for Biodiversity and Ecological Restoration. Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/4h46m0ws>

Websites and Data Portals:

Big-Bee project website: <http://big-bee.net>

Bee Library Symbiota Portal: <https://library.big-bee.net>

Big-Bee focused Global Biotic Interactions project page:

<https://www.globalbioticinteractions.org/bigbee>

iDigBio Wiki:

[https://www.idigbio.org/wiki/index.php?title=TCN: Extending Anthophila research through image and trait digitization \(Big-Bee\)](https://www.idigbio.org/wiki/index.php?title=TCN:_Extending_Anthropila_research_through_image_and_trait_digitization_(Big-Bee))

Big-Bee Network GitHub Project: <https://github.com/Big-Bee-Network>

YouTube (Macroscopic Solutions): <https://macroscopicolutions.com/video-tutorial-big-bee-tcn;>

<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCXhbJ-JirA3-J7FihjXtUyg>

Notes from Nature Big-Bee Bonanza project:

<https://www.zooniverse.org/projects/md68135/notes-from-nature-big-bee-bonanza>

Other Publications (Datasets and Reports):

1. Seltmann, K. C., Poelen, J. H., & Global Biotic Interaction Community. (2025). Global Bee Interaction Data (v6.0) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17715382>

2. Seltmann, K. C., Poelen, J. H., & Global Biotic Interaction Community. (2024). Global Bee Interaction Data (v4.0) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12639658>
3. Armstead, S., Carper, A. L., Davidson, D., Blanchard, M., Hopwood, J., Larcom, R., Black, S., Briles, C., Irwin, R., Jolma, G., Resasco, J., Davis, S., Mola, J., and D. Inouye. 308 pp. 2024. Colorado Native Pollinating Insects Health Study. Denver: Colorado Department of Natural Resources.
<https://dnr.colorado.gov/native-pollinating-insects-health-study>
4. Poelen, JH (ed .) . (2024). Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources
hash://sha256/83617875e84bb8ae7ac2a257ad50eb8e82d8935d975f465b8ee8f3a803f72b48 hash://md5/c639d7e3fcd5603f6c48e9d5e6c49672 (0.24) [Data set]. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11105453>
5. José Augusto Salim, & Jorrit Poelen. (2024). globalbioticinteractions/nomer: 0.5.13 (0.5.13). Zenodo. <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.1145474>
6. Seltmann, K., & Poelen, J. (2024). Tab and comma delimited versions of Discover Life bee species guide and world checklist (Hymenoptera: Apoidea: Anthophila) (56.1) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10019874>
7. Smith, C., Reyes, S., Ryan, K. A., Smith, M., Deer, E., Sanchez, E., Sheccid, R. T., Kung, G.-A., Carper, A. L., & Seltmann, K. (2024). UCSB's 3D imaging and modeling protocol. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10594883>
8. Seltmann, K. (2024). Exhibit at California Nature Art Museum, San Luis Obispo, CA: The Birds and the Bees and More: Pollinators
hash://md5/4f552ae78473131eafb39657f95c6260. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10612006>
9. Seltmann, Katja C., Poelen, Jorrit H., Allen, Julie, Eldredge, K. Taro, Engel, Michael, Gonzalez, Victor, Knowles, L. Lacey, & Horsley, Pam. (2023) Big-Bee indexed biotic interactions and review summary (0.8.0) [Data set]. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8184843>
10. Seltmann, K. C., Poelen, J. H., Allen, J., Eldredge, K. T., Engel, M., Gonzalez, V., Knowles, L. L., & Horsley, P. (2023). Big Bee indexed biotic interactions and review summary (0.8.0) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8184843>
11. Brianne Du Clos, Julien Brun, Sam Droege, Jen Hammock, Andrew Johnston, Jonathan Koch, Clare Maffei, Cynthia Sims Parr, Jorrit H. Poelen, Katja C. Seltmann, & Erika M. Tucker. (2023) US National Native Bee Monitoring RCN Data Management Workshop: Public Domain Videos (1.0.0). Zenodo. doi:10.5281/zenodo.7868217.
12. Seltmann, Katja C., Poelen, Jorrit H., Allen, Julie, Eldredge, K. Taro, Engel, Michael, Gonzalez, Victor, Knowles, L. Lacey, & Horsley, Pam. (2023) Big-Bee indexed biotic interactions and review summary (0.7.0) [Data set]. Zenodo.
doi:10.5281/zenodo.7865367
13. Miller, JT, Poelen, Jorrit, & Seltmann, Katja. (2023) Big-Bee Name Alignment Workshop. Zenodo. 10.5281/zenodo.7829969.
14. Seltmann, Katja, Poelen, Jorrit H., UCSB Natural History Collections, & Big-Bee Community. (2023) *Halictus ligatus* Halictidae UCSB-IZC00036803
<https://library.big-bee.net/portal/collections/individual/index.php?occid=72096>

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7510912>
16. Katja C. Seltmann, & Global Biotic Interaction Community. (2022) Global Bee Interaction Data (v2.02) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6564718>
17. Seltmann, Katja C., Poelen, Jorrit H., Allen, Julie, Eldredge, Taro, Engel, Michael, & Gonzalez, Victor. (2022) Big-Bee indexed biotic interactions and review summary (0.4.0) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6950082>
18. Seltmann, Katja C., Poelen, Jorrit H., Engel, Michael, & Gonzalez, Victor. (2022) Big-Bee indexed biotic interactions and review summary (0.3.0) [Data set]. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5915012>
19. Seltmann, Katja C., & Poelen, Jorrit H. (2022) Big-Bee indexed biotic interactions and review summary (0.2.2) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5915003>
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20. Publications of Big-Bee Images: Big-Bee Community, Poelen, Jorrit H., & Seltmann, Katja. (2022) Xylocopa sonorina - UCSB-IZC00012194 - Bee Library - 73e389aa-5886-4c48-8778-ba8932d1bd7e
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<https://escholarship.org/uc/item/2vm761mv>

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2. Chamberlain, J. (2025) The Buzz Around the bee exhibit: A look at Santa Barbara's pollinators. The Daily Nexus. March 6, 2025.
<https://dailynexus.com/2025-03-06/the-buzz-around-the-bee-exhibit-a-look-at-santa-barbaras-pollinators>
3. Spinner, A. (2025). The Three-Century Lifespan of the Modern Bee, The Long Now (<https://longnow.org/ideas/the-three-century-lifespan-of-the-modern-bee/>) on August 30, 2023.

4. Matt Kettmann. Bee Happy. UC Santa Barbara Magazine Retrieved from <https://magazine.ucsb.edu/spring-summer-2022/bee-happy> on July 25, 2022.
5. Tara Duggan. (2021). To help fight the loss of bees, the California Academy of Sciences shared a 180,000-strong collection online. San Francisco Chronicle. Retrieved from <https://www.sfchronicle.com/climate/article/To-help-fight-loss-of-bees-California-Academy-of-16570034.php> on 2 Nov 2021.
6. Shelly Leachman (2021). Creating a Buzz. UCSB Current. Retrieved from <https://www.news.ucsb.edu/2021/020448/creating-buzz> on 27 Oct 2021.

Participants

13 institutions are funded by the Big-Bee project (Table 4). Lead participants and institution codes are listed below from each institution. A total of **141** people worked on the Big-Bee project, including PIs, collection managers, students, volunteers, technicians, and postdoctoral scholars this year (Table 5). **34** undergraduate students received some financial compensation for the project, and **35** students received course credit. **6** graduate students and **1** postdoctoral scholar contributed to the project. UCR was not active this year as they completed their subcontract the prior year. Jody Martin (LACM PI) was replaced by Megan Barkdull as the new LACM PI.

Institution	Institution Code	Participant	Institution affiliation
Arizona State University	ASUHIC	Nico Franz	School of Life Sciences, Hasbrouck Insect Collection
		Ed Gilbert	School of Life Sciences
		Sangmi Lee	Hasbrouck Insect Collection
California Academy of Sciences	CAS	Chris Grinter	California Academy of Sciences, Entomology
Florida State Collection of Arthropods	FSCA	Elijah Talamas	Florida Department of Agriculture and Consumer Services, Division of Plant Industry
Harvard University	MCZ	Naomi Pierce	Department of Organismic and Evolutionary Biology, Museum of Comparative Zoology
		Crystal Maier	Museum of Comparative Zoology, Entomology
Natural History Museum of Los Angeles County	LACM	Megan Barkdull	Natural History Museum, Los Angeles County, Entomology
		Giar-Ann Kung	Natural History Museum, Los Angeles County, Entomology
San Diego Natural History Museum	SDMC	Pamela Horsley	San Diego Natural History Museum, Entomology

University of California-Berkeley	EMEC	Neil Tsutsui	Department of Environmental Science, Policy and Management
		Peter Oboyski	Essig Museum of Entomology
University of California, Santa Barbara	UCSB	Katja C Seltmann	Cheadle Center for Biodiversity and Ecological Restoration, Earth Research Institute
University of Colorado, Boulder	UCMC	Adrian Carper	Museum of Natural History, Entomology
		Virginia Scott	Museum of Natural History, Entomology
University of Kansas	SEMC	Victor Gonzalez-Betancourt	Department of Natural Sciences and Mathematics - Ecology & Evolutionary Biology, KU Biodiversity Institute
University of Michigan Museum of Zoology	UMMZ	L. Lacey Knowles	University of Michigan Museum of Zoology Insect Collection
		Taro Eldredge	University of Michigan Museum of Zoology Insect Collection
University of Nevada, Reno	UNR	Julie Allen	Department of Biology
University of New Hampshire	UNHC	Istvan Miko	Donald S. Chandler Entomological Collection

Table 4: List of project PIs and lead participants at each Big-Bee funded institution.

	UNHC	UMMZ	UCSB	FSCA	SEMC	SDMC	UCMC	CAS	EMEC	LACM	ASUHC	MCZ	Total
Undergraduate students hired (i.e., paid)	3	9	5	0	2	0	0	0	11	0	4	0	34
Undergraduate students working for course credit	0	0	24	0	0	0	0	0	7	0	4	0	35
Undergraduate student volunteers	1	0	0	0	0	5	0	0	1	0	6	0	13
Non-student volunteers	1	0	0	0	0	4	0	4	0	0	0	0	9
Total number of undergraduate students	3	9	29	0	2	3	0	0	19	0	14	0	79
Graduate students	0	1	3	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	6
Non-student staff	1	3	1	3	1	9	2	3	3	3	2	3	34
Total number of people	7	13	34	4	4	20	2	7	24	3	18	5	141

Table 5: Number of people involved in Big-Bee during 24-25.

Partner Organizations

- Notes from Nature
- US National Native Bee Monitoring RCN
- iDigBio
- Biodiversity Information Standards (TDWG)
- Symbiota Support Hub (iDigBio & ASU)
- USGS Native Bee Inventory and Monitoring Lab
- Macroscopic Solutions, LLC

Other Collaborators

Erika Tucker - Terrestrial Parasite Tracker Digitization Taxonomy Manager, Milwaukee Public Museum; Research Associate, Biodiversity Outreach Network (BON); iDigBees

Hollis Woodard - Assistant Professor, University of California - Riverside; PI USDA US National Native Bee Monitoring RCN (<https://www.usnativebees.com>)

Elizabeth Hill - Agricultural Research Service, US Department of Agriculture
Andrew Johnson - Invertebrate Collections Manager - NEON Biorepository, Arizona State University, Symbiota Support Hub

Andrew Johnston - Formerly ASU, Neon Biorepository, Symbiota Support Hub (iDigBio & ASU); Presently Purdue University

Katie Pearson - Symbiota Support Hub (iDigBio & ASU); CAP TCN

Lindsay Walker - Symbiota Support Hub (iDigBio & ASU)

Thomas van de Kamp - Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, Laboratory for Applications of Synchrotron Radiation

Robert Guralnick - Curator of Biodiversity Informatics, Florida Museum of Natural History, University of Florida, iDigBio, Notes from Nature

Impacts

What is the impact on the development of the principal discipline(s) of the project?

Big-Bee promoted the use of specimen data and collections expertise in research by integrating AI and creating larger datasets for reuse, and we evaluated our digitization products through preliminary research (posters) and peer-reviewed publications. A clear example is our AI-enabled trait work: “Climate explains global functional trait variation in bees” leverages deep learning/computer vision to quantify complex traits (e.g., hair coverage and lightness) directly from museum specimen images, showing how standardized digitized specimens can support global, trait-based inference rather than serving only as static references.

Complementing this, “Toward a functional trait approach to bee ecology” provides a community roadmap for trait standards and sharing, aligning digitization outputs with tractable research questions and reusable data structures.

Big-Bee also advanced biodiversity informatics by publishing and integrating large interaction datasets for synthesis. The Authorea dataset paper “Tackling the Eltonian shortfall for bees using the Global Biotic Interactions dataset” describes a refined bee–plant interaction dataset with 482,617 unique interaction records linking 4,560 bee species and 8,651 plant taxa, while explicitly documenting taxonomic and geographic bias, turning unstructured interaction records into a research-ready resource and making limitations transparent for downstream analyses and model development. This builds on GloBI’s role as an open infrastructure that aggregates interaction datasets using open-source software.

Finally, Big-Bee expanded computational specimen use beyond 2D by promoting quantitative 3D approaches. In “Estimating body size in the large carpenter bees (*Xylocopa*)”, we demonstrate body-size proxies and highlight a photogrammetry/3D modeling application to estimate surface area and volume, illustrating how digitized specimens can support new measurement modalities and transferable protocols.

Additionally, we were an important collections and informatics voice as part of an enlarging U.S. National Native Bee Monitoring Network that includes US federal agencies (USDA, USFWS) and NGOs. The National Native Bee Monitoring Research & Coordination Network (funded through USDA-NIFA’s Pollinator Health Program) is coordinating the monitoring community and producing standardized protocols and data practices to enable interoperable, scalable monitoring and a future unified national program. The connection is especially explicit in the Journal of Melittology special issue series (a Network product): it pairs field protocols with a data-management framework, the Wild Bee Data Standard, co-authored by Seltmann, which helps ensure that monitoring and specimen/occurrence records can be recorded and shared consistently through platforms like Symbiota portals (including the Bee Library) and onward to aggregators such as GBIF. This relationship is also reinforced by PI Victor H. Gonzalez, who serves as Editor-in-Chief of the Journal of Melittology and is acknowledged for leadership supporting the special issue’s publication, helping make these community standards visible, citable, and easy to adopt.

UCSB developed a SPNHC symposium submission with RANGES TCN (David Bloom, Rob Guralnick, Bryan McLean) titled “The (over) extended specimen: why are these data so difficult to share?” as an open forum to discuss the challenges and success of trait data sharing within these projects.

What is the impact on other disciplines?

Big-Bee continues to seek partners for developing artificial intelligence and improved 3D modeling applications using Big-Bee images. Seltmann mentored students from UCSB Statistics and Applied Probability Department for a Data Science Capstone in all years of the project. In 2024-25 the capstone focused on developing a LLM for bee taxonomy. This poster describes Chat G-Bee-T, a domain-specific, multimodal retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) chatbot built to streamline bee taxonomy and identification workflows for the Big-Bee Lab. It outlines a pipeline that ingests core bee resources (PDF textbooks and keys, CSV datasets of occurrences/interactions/taxonomy, and glossary text), cleans and chunks them, extracts figures

and captions, converts dichotomous keys into a tree-like structure, and then uses a vector store to ground chatbot responses with linked sources and definitions; advisor evaluation found strong clarity, with correctness/completeness improving through prompt optimization and planned future work (interactive keys, expanded database, and more systematic evaluation). The impact includes focused training in conservation issues for future data science professionals.

Reagan, S. C, Bishop, B., Linden, C., Sharma, K., Yan, D., & Dibley, K. (2025). Exploring Optimizations in Anthophila Taxonomic Research Using Retrieval-Augmented Generation. UC Santa Barbara: Cheadle Center for Biodiversity and Ecological Restoration. Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/8xc790xx>

Big-Bee continued to promote the sharing of images under Creative Commons 0/Public Domain licenses, which already has received attention from MediaWiki and computer vision bee identification initiatives (Brian Spiesman - <https://beemachine.ai>; Automated Wildlife Monitoring - <https://automated-wildlife-cig.github.io>; National Bee Diagnostic Centre (NBDC) - <https://www.nwpolytech.ca/research/national-bee-diagnostic-centre>) that are actively searching for open images of bees. Open access to images is also an important impact in the realm of technology transfer.

The San Diego Natural History Museum (SDMC) is collaborating with the Qualcomm Institute via the Academic Internship Program (AIP) at UC San Diego to continue refining 3D modelling capability, use artificial intelligence, and develop LLMs using Big-Bee SDMC open access image data sets. So far, 4 undergraduates and 1 graduate student have been working with PI Horsley.

What is the impact on the development of human resources?

This year, UCSB awarded three paid, full-time internships to students identified through the UCSB Office of Education Partnerships, the Smithsonian Scholars Program, and the UCSB Fuerte Program. The interns supported Big-Bee by imaging bees and participating in research, gaining hands-on experience with collections-based science, digitization workflows, and data practices. The UCSB Office of Education Partnerships works to increase college-going rates for low-income students and students who will be the first in their families to pursue higher education. The UCSB Fuerte Program supports retention and academic success for students from underrepresented backgrounds through mentoring and professional development, helping interns build skills and clearer pathways into biodiversity and conservation careers.

This project has aided in the success of many of its participants. PI Carper, accepted a position with Colorado Parks and Wildlife as the statewide Pollinator Conservation Program Manager, as part of a new 5-person Species Conservation of Invertebrates and Plants team. He was appointed Entomology Curator Adjoint in 2024 to continue his research and has assisted Collections Manager V. Scott with remaining activities associated with the Big-Bee project.

UCSB postdoctoral scholar Colleen Smith was appointed in 2024 as a Biologist at the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, and Madeleine Ostwald was hired in 2025 as a faculty Lecturer in Ecology, Conservation, & Biodiversity, Queen Mary, London.

Undergraduate students and recent graduate students hired as technicians gained valuable experience working in scientific collections. Their invaluable contributions to the Big-Bee Project resulted in students gaining skills in specimen curation, photography and image editing, 3D photogrammetry software, computer programming, research hypothesis testing and experiment execution. As a result, many participants have continued their educational pursuits via graduate studies (UCSB Zoe Wood now at UC Davis with Dr. Emily Meineke) and recent graduates have obtained employment in related fields as a direct result of the experience and skills gained during the Big-Bee Project (SDMC Ellie Deer at Mikhail Ogawa Engineering).

What is the impact on teaching and education experiences?

The collaborative efforts of Big-Bee and its committed team of educators, researchers, and mentors have paved the way for a thriving environment that encourages undergraduate participation in research and fosters the development of future biodiversity experts and collection managers. Undergraduate students make up a large proportion of the workforce in university collections. Big-Bee has already demonstrated a commitment to training the next generation of collection managers and biodiversity researchers about the use and importance of natural history collections. Big-Bee institutions hired **34** undergraduate students, **35** participated for course credit and **13** as volunteers. The students gave **5** oral presentations about Big-Bee and **11** posters. These numbers are fairly consistent with last year. There were **15** undergraduate research projects across the Big-Bee network.

All institutions created value-added activities for undergraduates, staff, and the public. For example, Seltmann and UCSB postdoc Maddie Ostwald co-mentored a Statistics and Applied Probability Department capstone course focused on extraction and evaluation of wing venation from bee images. The students developed a bee identification app from wings and explored other methods for classifying morphotypes based on supervised and unsupervised clustering methods. This is potentially transformative as it could provide quantitative methods for sorting bees to morphotype, thus improving ecological studies

What is the impact on physical resources that form infrastructure?

Nothing to report.

What is the impact on institutional resources that form infrastructure?

Nothing to report.

What is the impact on information resources that form infrastructure?

Nothing to report.

What is the impact on technology transfer?

For Big-Bee, the impact on technology transfer is that we developed means of turning specimen digitization and bespoke biodiversity workflows into portable protocols, standards, software-enabled infrastructure, and open data products that other collections, monitoring programs, and those interested in the intersection of AI and biodiversity can be inspired by or adopt. Concretely, Big-Bee transferred (1) data standardization and publishing practices through

peer-reviewed outputs like the Wild Bee Data Standard (Du Clos et al. 2025, Journal of Melittology, <https://doi.org/10.17161/jom.vi123.23163>) and the controlled-vocabulary implementation report for Audubon Core terms (Baskauf et al. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.3897/biss.7.94188>), which provide re-usable templates, term guidance, and decision frameworks that agencies and labs can apply to their own occurrence and media data; (2) We shared deployable cyberinfrastructure via the Bee Library Symbiota portal (<https://library.big-bee.net>) and the broader Big-Bee web/GitHub footprint (<http://big-bee.net> ; <https://github.com/Big-Bee-Network>), which function as example platforms for aggregating records, serving images/traits, and pushing standardized datasets onward to aggregators (e.g., GBIF); and (3) novel trait digitization methods, demonstrated by the Notes from Nature Big-Bee Bonanza project (<https://www.zooniverse.org/projects/md68135/notes-from-nature-big-bee-bonanza>) and validated in Ecology and Evolution (“Leveraging community science to measure bee body size...”, Ostwald et al. 2025, <https://doi.org/10.1002/ece3.71665>), showing that community-science measurement and transcription can be operationalized and reused beyond Big-Bee.

Big-Bee also expanded technology transfer into 3D specimen digitization by working with Macroscopic Solutions to develop and disseminate practical 3D modeling protocols and trainings (video tutorials: <https://macroscopicsolutions.com/video-tutorial-big-bee-tcn> and YouTube channel), complemented by an openly released UCSB 3D imaging and modeling protocol on Zenodo (Smith et al. 2024, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10594883>). To keep our 3D bee models tightly linked to the image data that support them (e.g., texture maps, turntables, source images), we centralize the full asset bundles in the CyVerse Data Store (built on iRODS), which is designed for secure collaboration and sharing of research data at scale. CyVerse. We organize each specimen as a self-contained folder (model + textures + images + derived products + README/metadata) and grant collaborators controlled access using CyVerse’s granular sharing permissions (read, write, own), so partners can contribute updates and link to specimen records in the bee library Symbiota portal. Finally, Big-Bee’s open datasets and pipelines, especially in biotic interactions (e.g., GloBI Big-Bee page: <https://www.globalbioticinteractions.org/bigbee>; Global Bee Interaction Data v4.0: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12639658>; and the “indexed biotic interactions and review summary” Zenodo series), represent transferable technology because they package repeatable extraction, indexing, and publication approaches that other projects can replicate for different taxa or regions.

What is the impact on society beyond science and technology?

One of the largest impacts of the project is our commitment to increasing awareness about bees and other insects in our communities. This comes through outreach events, including support for Xerces Society conservation initiatives such as the Bee Campus program (UCB & UCSB), pollinator gardens, or bug-themed museum events. An estimated total of **19,474** people attended Big-Bee related events. A few examples from this year include UC Berkeley (EMEC) hosted hundreds of students and community members through Xerces Bee Campus outreach programs and Homecoming/Alumni events highlighting Big-Bee and the importance of collections. Other museums hosted numerous behind-the-scenes tours and public outreach

events related to pollinators, highlighting the products of the Big-Bee Project (SDMC Nat Talk about Pollinators, 150th anniversary celebrations; LACM Earth Day and Bug Fair events; SEMC “Hasta Luego Monarchs” at the Pollinator Prairie; ASUHC Butterfly Wonderland event).

What percentage of the award's budget was spent in a foreign country?

Nothing to report.

Actual or Anticipated problems or delays and actions or plans to resolve them:

Individual institutional challenges are addressed in each collaborator’s report, but a few network-wide constraints stood out. First, the Canon DSLR cameras used for 3D photogrammetry were subjected to heavy use and periodically triggered Error 20 and 30 codes, most often associated with shutter failures driven by the large number of images required for 3D workflows (approximately 2,000 to 8,000 images per specimen). Typical repairs took about 10 to 20 days; however, the impact on productivity would have been much worse without the exceptional customer service and sustained effort from Macroscopic Solutions. Their rapid troubleshooting and frequent provision of loaner cameras and flashes during repairs reduced downtime (but did not prevent it) and helped institutions maintain continuity in imaging schedules. They also worked closely with Nikon to limit repair costs for partner institutions. This persistent constraint informed future imaging decisions, including Macroscopic Solutions’ consideration of mirrorless systems for high-throughput 3D workflows.

Second, training for high-resolution 2D and 3D imaging was delivered remotely, in part because the project launched during COVID-related travel restrictions. Remote training was successful, but many institutions would have benefited from in-person instruction, and several partners noted that Macropod-based imaging functioned as an expert workflow rather than low-skill digitization. This level of technical expertise differs from what has been required for many past ADBC projects, where primary digitization tasks were typically optimized for higher-throughput, more standardized imaging and transcription workflows. In Big-Bee, consistent production of publishable, analysis-ready high-resolution images and 3D datasets depended on dedicated people and careful quality control, with more hands-on involvement from the PIs than expected. As a result, institutions with high participant turnover or undergraduate-heavy staffing models were generally less successful in high-resolution imaging than those with stable staffing and dedicated imaging expertise. As other TCNs have done in the past, we were opportunistic in using volunteers or unpaid labor to keep costs per specimen low. This strategy was less effective for this type of digitization and contributed to lower-than-anticipated digitization output.

Finally, although still a very important part of our cumulative outcomes, 3D photogrammetry proved more difficult and time-consuming than anticipated, and some institutions chose not to pursue 3D imaging in order to prioritize specimen occurrence digitization. A 3D model required approximately 140 focus-stacked images, with each focus-stacked image consisting of 70 or more source images. One image suite took approximately eight hours to capture and process. Timing and staffing were again limiting factors. Although imaging could run overnight, technical staff needed to be present in both the afternoon and the morning to manage acquisition and processing. In practice, this was difficult to schedule using volunteer or part-time labor.

Although this was the final year of the award, high-resolution imaging, especially 3D, was expected to continue at KU and UCSB (and at select partner sites) to support BeeMachine training data and to enable ongoing, derivative research using 3D volume and surface-area measurements.